

13th INTERNATIONAL
CONGRESS
OF THE SERBIAN SOCIETY
OF TOXICOLOGY

1st TOXSEE
REGIONAL
CONFERENCE

Present and Future of toxicology: Challenges and opportunities

10 - 12 May, 2023 Belgrade

electronic

ABSTRACT
BOOK

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DEAR COLLEAGUES, DEAR FRIENDS,

We are delighted to greet you on the **13th International Congress of the Serbian Society of Toxicology & 1. TOXSEE Regional Conference - Present and Future of toxicology: challenges and opportunities**, organized in Belgrade from 10-12 May 2023.

Five years after our last international Congress we gathered in Belgrade, to further promote contemporary toxicology, in the broadest sense of meaning, as a response to the new challenges requiring innovative approaches and solutions, as it is understood in the third decade of the XXI century.

Initial concept, to blend the top scientific level in toxicology with the potentials of its' use in broad array of clinical and other domains, proved to be right. Line-up of more than 70 first class international and regional faculties as well as best Serbian scientists and toxicology professionals in all related domains fully justify the approach. Moreover, interest and presence of more than 250 colleagues from Serbia and region witness that our professional community has recognized the approach taken and shown vast interest.

The Serbian Society of Toxicology is committed to innovation and creativity in research and education, in cooperation with collegial associations and institutions in Serbia and abroad. As a regional leader, we developed and inaugurated the regional brand TOXSEE, with the idea to gather as much as possible expertise and know-how from the region and Europe, to capture knowledge, share experience and exchange practical skills with colleagues who deal with toxicology problems daily.

Time imposes on us the need to integrate science, top knowledge and daily practice in a quality and efficient way, to contribute to the better health of the society as a whole in the most purposeful manner. Therefore, a thematic and functional connections with domains of emergency medicine, general medicine, paediatrics, ecology, in addition to already standard toxicological disciplines i.e. clinical, forensic, occupational, and experimental toxicology have been enhanced.

We are glad to host you in a pleasant atmosphere of Belgrade in mid-May, to benefit from the attractive and dynamic program, exchange knowledge, and, equally important, to refresh existing and establish new contacts with colleagues and friends, while enjoying our hospitality and cherish the moment in one of the best partying cities of Europe.

YOU ARE MOST WELCOME!!!

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- President of the 13th STC Congress

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ANTIOKSIDANTNI EFEKAT SOJINIH IZOFLAVONA I PROBIOTIKA NA OKSIDATIVNI STRES PACOVA IZLOŽENIH UGLJEN TETRAHLORIDU

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UVOD: Zdravstvene prednosti sojinih izoflavona se često pripisuju njihovoj antioksidantnoj aktivnosti. Kako crevni mikrobiom ima veliki uticaj na metabolizam izoflavona, probiotici bi mogli povećati njihovu bioraspoloživost i in vivo antioksidantni potencijal.

CILJ: Cilj je bio da se proceni antioksidantna aktivnost sojinih izoflavona, probiotika i njihove kombinacije na oksidativni stres izazvan ugljen tetrahloridom (CCl₄) kod pacova.

METODOLOGIJA: Wistar pacovi su raspoređeni u sedam grupa po šest životinja: grupa I – kontrola; II – izoflavoni soje (50 mg/kg); III – probiotici (10⁹ CFU/kg); IV – CCl₄ i.p. (1 mg/kg); V-VII – nakon doze CCl₄, hranjene izoflavonima, probioticima i njihovom kombinacijom, redom, tokom 15 dana, nakon čega su životinje žrtvovane. U serumu su određivani ukupni antioksidantni status (TAS), alanin aminotransferaza (ALT) i aspartat aminotransferaza (AST). U tkivima jetre i bubrega merena je lipidna peroksidacija (TBARS), aktivnosti katalaze (CAT) i glutation-S-transferaze (GST).

REZULTATI: Poređenjem rezultata dobijenih u CCl₄ grupi (IV) sa tretiranim grupama (V-VII), pokazalo se da su izoflavoni statistički značajno (p=0,003) povećali TAS. Probiotici (p

ZAKLJUČAK: Kod većine analiziranih parametara, kombinacija izoflavona i probiotika se pokazala kao najsnažnija u ublažavanju oksidativnog stresa izazvanog CCl₄.

KLJUČNE REČI: izoflavoni, probiotici, pacovi, ugljen tetrahlorid, oksidativni stress